

**A STUDY ON WORK LIFE BALANCE AND GLASS
CEILING FACED BY WOMEN EMPLOYEES IN
EDUCATION SECTOR**

SYNOPSIS

**Thesis to be submitted to College of Management & Commerce, Srinivas
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SYNOPSIS

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1. INTRODUCTION

Work-Life Balance (WLB) involves the interaction between the commitments for the paid work with any organization and the unpaid work responsibilities of the family, community and personal development. Work-life has become a major issue faced by employed women in daily life. The level of balance maintained in this regard varies from women to women. Work-Life Balance drastically impacts on the decision making, productivity and administrative capacity of all types of workers including skilled and unskilled employees at all levels. Generally, the social, economic and demographic factors have intensively influenced the personal and professional lives of women. Work-Life Balance is not of recent origin. The Industrial Revolution introduced during the second half of the eighteenth Century have brought in changes in the employment scenario and the working environment introduced a new interpretation of the concept of Work-Life Balance. The topic gained momentum over the years with the advancement of women into the corporate world when social expectations continued with the view that women are constrained majorly to family commitments. The stereotyped social stigma that men have the sole right to work outside and women to take up family care along with household chores have curtailed women from excelling in her concerned career. Work-Life Balance is creating a productive work culture to reduce the imbalance caused between the work and other parts of people's lives. It is considered to be the combination of appropriate employment opportunities, supporting organizational systems and supportive management. It creates the right combination of participation in paid work governed based on working conditions with the other aspects of the personal lives of employees. In a more generally held view work-life balance is the flexible work strategies to achieve a proper balance between Work and Personal Responsibilities. Widespread education and industrialization have intensified the competition and economic sustainability has become a challenge putting pressure upon all the family members to work to augment income. In this regard, the need to maintain congenial working conditions where employees could able to balance work with their individual requirements has become an important factor for the organizations to retain its efficient workforce and to improve organizational productivity. Globalization and changing trends in employment have redefined the work as pleasure and passion. Along with the problem

of Work-Life Balance faced by women they are also the victims of “Glass Ceiling” which is known to be the unseen barriers that prevent women from climbing the ladder of hierarchy in the profession. Despite the entry and participation of women in varied professions and making their presence felt in varied fields, they are deprived of opportunities to excel in many professions. Moreover, the access for women to higher levels of organizations are limited in the male-dominated society causing under-representation to women at higher levels of hierarchy. With the increase in the number of women employees in the educational sector, the concept of work-life balance and glass ceiling is becoming a more relevant branch of study in twenty-first century.

2. RESEARCH BACKGROUND

Research shows the importance of work-life balance since it is related to the psychological wellbeing of an employee and also overall harmony in life. Work-Life Balance is contentment and good working at work and home with a minimal role clash. Work-life Balance has also been expressed as a person’s ability to meet family and work commitment as well as non-work responsibilities and other activities. These definitions for work-life balance indicate creating an acceptable situation of work and life. The majority of the studies on work-life balance have defined work-Life balance in the aspect of the level of work-life conflict. Before the emergence of industries and the growth of economies, families were primarily involved in the production of their consumption. In the later years with the increase in industrialization and the growth in the market economies more workplaces were created outside the homes and organizations became in charge of production. Because family and work are separate and since traditionally men assumed the breadwinner’s role and women assumed the homemaker's role researchers in the early stages considered as if work and family systems functioned independently. Studies on work and family showed an open systems approach wherein researchers felt that events and activities at the workplace affected events and activities at home and vice versa. ‘Spillover theory’ which is an example of an open system approach proposed that even though there are boundaries between Family and work, behaviors and emotions in one area will carry over to other areas. In complimentary to spillover theory is Compensatory theory which says that there exists an inverse relationship between family and work. Here people attempt to make up for what that is missing in the other by making differing investments. Individuals whose family life is unsatisfying will try to carry out work activities that give them satisfaction and vice versa. Spill over and compensatory theory though proposed that work and family are interdependent were of limited use since it did not adequately predict, explain and solve the

problems faced by individuals while balancing home and work responsibilities. Work/family border theory was thus developed as a remedy to overcome the gaps of previous theories. This theory explains how individuals manage the work and family areas and borders between them to maintain balance. Work-life balance is an indicator of the role in family and role in the workplace. Work /Family border theory explains the complex interaction between border crossers, humans transiting between family and work systems, prediction as to when the conflict will occur and has 'given a framework to attain work-life balance. The changes taking place in the Indian Economy is resulting in changes in the role of women from customary to rationalized culture has influenced women to enter into the workforce to support the family by maintaining a positive equilibrium between work and life. Previous research has stated that competition has driven organizations to be more responsive to changes by making employees more flexible, acclimatized and responsive to changes such as stretched work hours, workload and Job Stress. These changes affect domestic chores, family responsibility, child and eldercare resulting in inefficiency to fulfill family obligations. The relationship between work and family-related conflict has been studied among employees working in different establishments such as Hotels, Hospitals, Security firms, Software firms, and construction. Studies specifically have shown that the work-family conflict is connected to Reduced job Satisfaction, Increased employee turnover, low employee performance, and reduced employee commitment. Developing individual and organizational work-life balance strategies exhibited better well-being, health conditions and achieved work-life balance than those do not practice. The literature recognizes that employee well-being and health can be affected by many reasons such as work stress, level of job control by individual employee, work and family conflict and also the absence of organizational support along with demographic variables such as age and also gender. These studies show the connection between an individual's well-being and the ability to manage work-life conflict and work-life policy support. Moreover, women have enormous potential to provide to the organization and recent literature shows that women leaders are linked with great innovation, profitability, better consumer outreach and better records in corporate social responsibilities. Women in higher ranks also increase chances for women in lower ranks reducing overall gender discrimination. In spite of this women still, remain considerably underrepresented in leadership positions. In India growth of Higher education institutions has been rapid with the growth of the economy. India has experienced an increased number of private and public universities, an increase in the number of diversified courses in all fields', extreme growth of student enrolment and also increase in the usage of web-based teaching. This increasingly high demanding environment has resulted in increased complexity

of the academic work among university academic staff. The traditional role of universities was based on teaching, research and service or administration, where the primary emphasis was on teaching and research and administration was considered secondary. Now universities have been regarded as the place of “Knowledge society” which has reflected on the increased workload, expectations for measurable outputs of faculties, overall performance accountability and responsiveness towards societal and student needs. University faculties are said to be facing increasing challenges by increased workload and accountability. Research carried on in academic workloads has shown the increase of academic work as well as maintaining a balance between teaching and research since the government has embraced performance as a component for funding research budget for higher education. Studies have also shown the impact of increasing demand in higher education on stress and the work-life balance of staff. These changes illustrate the complexity of the academic area in an ever-increasing and demanding environment. Universities are the largest ‘knowledge-based’ institutions in the given region which are insisted by the industries and policymakers to transform their traditional roles which includes teaching and research by including an additional crucial role in economic regional development. This tells us that University academics or studies are expected to help economic regeneration by spreading their expertise and knowledge through industry-linked partnerships. Nevertheless, each party i.e Government, University Management, policymakers, and society should understand that too many demands on the university staff can result in vagueness in terms of academic roles and can lead to a work conflict. Lack of role clarity results in role ambiguity and conflict which has a definite impact on the achievement of personal goals as well as organizational goals. This results in employee anxiety, dissatisfaction and also organizational ineffectiveness. Multiple roles at the workplace by university academics along with pressure from organization and community are considered to be a significant factor that influences their state of work-life balance which in turn triggers their professional attitudes such as Job satisfaction, Organizational commitment and decision to leave the organization. Thus the present study concentrates on the Education sector with special reference to state Universities of Karnataka.

The review of the literature has provided several insights into the concept of work-life balance and Glass ceiling. The inference taken from the previous studies is that work-life balance and glass ceiling is a very important concept in all sectors, particularly in the Education sector. It has been observed in various studies that there is a linkage between work-life balance and the overall growth of Individuals and the sustainability of the organizations. This research is an

attempt to study the work-life balance and glass ceiling among women teachers of state universities in Karnataka. A study of this nature has not been identified especially in the state universities in the review of the literature. This study would further provide adequate information if socio-demographic variables influence work-life balance. It is an attempt to identify if these variables influence work-life balance in state universities of Karnataka. Karnataka being a hub for the education sector and people of this state have their distinct characteristics. This study thus is an attempt to determine the work-life balance and glass ceiling levels in this sector. The research has further attempted to identify the association and influence of challenges on work-life balance, its impact on Job satisfaction, Family satisfaction, Organizational commitment and employee performance, coping strategies, Legislative and Legal provisions enabling work-life balance and proceed towards a predictive model. Since a study of this nature has not been identified in the state of Karnataka concerning this sector, this study will add value to the knowledge of work-life balance and glass ceiling theoretically and would be useful in bringing balance in the life of individuals and universities.

3. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The Research design is exploratory and descriptive in nature. This research aims to understand the various issues, opportunities, and challenges connected with Work-Life Balance and Glass Ceiling faced by the women employees working in the Education sector in the state of Karnataka and to develop a predictive model on work-life balance. The theoretical framework of the study attempts to identify various challenges that influence work-life balance. The challenges that influence work-life balance can be categorized under three heads namely individual, family and organizational. The impact of work-life balance on job satisfaction, Organizational Commitment, Family Satisfaction, and employee performance has also been identified. Coping strategies or the practices adopted by women to maintain the work-life balance have been considered. The existence of the Glass ceiling and its relationship with work-life balance is identified in the study.

4. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

By considering the concepts of Work-Life Balance and Glass Ceiling of Women faculties in state Universities of Karnataka, objectives set forth for the study may be broadly be stated as below.

1. To analyze the Socio-Demographic status of the respondents and its influence on Work-Life Balance

2. To measure the work-life balance among Women teachers of State Universities in Karnataka.
3. To review the challenges faced by women in maintaining a work-life balance.
4. To find out the impact of work-life balance on job satisfaction, Organizational commitment, Family Satisfaction, and Employee performance.
5. To identify the practices and strategies towards maintaining a work-life balance.
6. To identify the Legislative provisions enabling work-life balance.
7. To measure the existence of the Glass Ceiling and its Relationship with work-life balance.
8. To Provide suggestions enabling women employees to maintain work-life balance and reduce Glass ceiling.

5. HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

Based on the above objectives following Hypothesis have been formulated:

- ❖ H₁1: There is an association between Demographic variables and work-life balance.
- ❖ H₁2: There is a relationship between challenges faced by women and work-life balance.
 - H₁2 (a): There is a relationship between challenges due to Individual factors and Work-life Balance
 - H₁2 (b): There is a relationship between challenges due to Family factors and Work-life Balance.
 - H₁2 (c): There is a relationship between challenges due to Organizational factors and Work-life Balance.
- ❖ H₁3: Work-life balance has an impact on Job Satisfaction
- ❖ H₁4: Work-life balance has an impact on Organizational commitment
- ❖ H₁5: Work-life balance has an impact on Family satisfaction
- ❖ H₁6: Work-life balance has an impact on Employee Performance
- ❖ H₁7: There is a relationship between work-life balance and coping strategies adopted by women
- ❖ H₁8: There is a relationship between work-life balance and legislative and judicial interventions
- ❖ H₁9: There is a relationship between the Glass ceiling and Work-life balance.

6. DATA SAMPLE AND METHODOLOGY

6.1 Sources of Data and Period of study:

The study focuses on primary as well as secondary data. Primary data is collected with the help of the Questionnaire method. To identify the relationship between Challenges such as Individual, Family and Organizational and work-life balance, as well as impact of work-life balance on Job Satisfaction, Organizational commitment, Family satisfaction and employee performance, coping strategies adopted by respondents, Legislative and Judicial intervention, existence of glass ceiling and its relationship with work-life balance the validated questionnaire is designed based on extensive Literature review. The structured questionnaire has been distributed to women teachers of State Universities of Karnataka who had the designations of Assistant Professor, Associate Professor, and Professor. The secondary data is derived from Journals, Books and Published University databases on the internet, etc. The study period is from 2010- 2019.

6.2 Sampling:

We have considered state universities listed by the University Grants Commission, a statutory organization of the Government of India which coordinates, determines and maintains standards of teaching, examination and research in the university Education in the year 2016-2017. We have selected 27 State universities based on the following criteria:

- The universities are listed by University Grants Commission.
- The Universities must have their domicile in Karnataka
- Only State Universities are selected for the study
- The universities must have class on the main campus

Based on the above criteria, the following Universities are selected:

Akkamahadevi Women's University, Bangalore University, Bengaluru Central University, Bengaluru North University, Davangere University, Gulbarga University, Kannada University, Karnataka State Law University, Karnataka State Open University, Karnataka University, Karnataka Veterinary, Animal and Fisheries Sciences University, Karnataka Folklore (Janapada University) University, Karnataka Sanskrith University, Karnataka State Rural Development and Panchayath Raj University, Karnataka State Dr. Gangubhai

Hangal Music and Performing Arts University, Kuvempu University, Mangalore University , University of Mysore, Rani Channamma University, Belgaum, Tumkur University, University of Agricultural Sciences, Bangalore, University of Agricultural Sciences, Dharwad, National law school of India University, University of Agricultural Sciences, Raichur, University of Horticultural Sciences, Bagalkot, Vesveswaraiah Technological University, Vijayanagara Sri Krishnadevaraya University.

The data is collected from 530 respondents from the sample universities. The entire population is considered for the study. Hence sampling technique is not applicable. When the questionnaires were thoroughly checked, 57 questionnaires were half-filled 51 were not returned and therefore, these questionnaires are excluded from the study. A final 422 sample respondents were included for further analysis. The above-discussed variables are hypothesized in the proposed model and examined the relationship by using descriptive statistics, Karl Pearson correlation coefficients, Fisher's exact test, and backward regression analysis. The response was collected for each component by using a 5-point Likert scale (1=Strongly Disagree, 2= Disagree, 3= Neutral, 4= Agree and 5= Strongly Agree). The reliability and validity of the questionnaire are examined Cronbach alpha coefficient test. Overall the questionnaire has 74 items with five variables. A pilot study is carried out for a sample size of 53.

From the pilot study, it was found that the scale used in the study is appropriate and reliable. The result of the pilot study is presented in the reliability test section. Descriptive analysis is done to know the nature and spread of the data. The Chi-square test and Fishers Exact test is used to know the relationship between demographic variables and work-life balance. Multiple regression analysis is also used to assess the impact of Individual factors, Family factors and organizational factors on work-life balance. In regression analysis, the work-life balance is the dependent variable and challenges such as Individual factors, Family factors, and organizational factors are the independent variables. Further, to know the relationship, the Karl Pearson correlation coefficient technique is used.

7. CHAPTER SCHEME

This study is organized in seven chapters. The description of each chapter is presented below:

Chapter 1: Conceptual Framework on Work-life Balance and Glass ceiling

This chapter discusses approaches to define Work-life Balance, theories on work-life Balance, work-life Balance Models, Challenges faced by women employees, effects of work-life

imbalance, Definition of the glass ceiling, strategies to cope with work-life Imbalance are discussed.

Chapter 2: Review of Literature

This section presents the literature into six parts. In the first part, literature related to demographic variables and work-life balance is presented. In the second part, Family-related variables and work-life balance are stated. In the third part, work-related variables and work-life balance are studied. In the fourth part, work-family conflict and work-life balance related literature are reviewed. Work-life balance and Job stress and Job Satisfaction are studied in the fifth part. Literature related to the Glass ceiling is presented in the sixth section.

Chapter 3: Research Design

The first chapter deals with the research design of the study. The design includes an introduction, statement of the problem, objectives of the study, and hypotheses of the study, data sample and methodology, sampling, result of reliability test, the proposed model for the study, the scope of the study, limitations of the study.

Chapter 4: Result and Discussion –Part I

Relationship of Socio-Demographic variables, Level of work-life balance, Association between socio-demographic variables and work-life balance and Challenges faced by Respondents

This chapter discusses the association Socio-demographic variables and work-life balance, the level of work-life balance and the challenges faced by women faculties under three domains such as Individual factors, Family Factors, and Organizational factors through descriptive analysis, Karl Pearson correlation coefficient and regression analysis are discussed.

Chapter 5: Result and Discussion- Part II

Impact of Work Life Balance, Coping Strategies, Legislative and Judicial Provisions and Glass ceiling

This chapter also includes the discussion of the mean score and the impact of work-life balance on job satisfaction, Organizational commitment, Family satisfaction, and employee performance. This chapter also discusses the level of Individual practices and strategies adopted by women and the level of Legislative and Judicial Provisions enabling work-life balance. Discussion of the existence of the glass ceiling and its relationship with work-life

balance is also done here. The results of descriptive statistics, Karl Pearson correlation coefficient is discussed.

Chapter 6: Results of the Proposed Model

The results of the proposed model for work-life balance and the sub-model for the demographic variables, challenges, Impact, coping strategies, Legislative and Judicial Provisions and Glass ceiling faced by women faculties are discussed in this chapter.

Chapter 7: Findings and Conclusion

In this chapter, we sum up our study by discussing the major findings of the fourth, fifth, and sixth chapter. The conclusions are drawn based on findings and suggestions.

References

This includes the references made in the study derived from secondary data that helps in identifying, formulating and solving the research problem.

Annexure

It incorporates a survey confined for the study, factors name, reliability statistics, the discriminant scores of the given information, drafted Questionnaire and values for the given set of information.

8. MAJOR FINDINGS

The results from the Chi-Square test indicates that the demographic variables such as Age, Residence type, Dwelling place, Income (Monthly), Qualification, Department, Total Experience, Experience in the present college, Hours worked per day, Family type, Family Size, Number of Dependents, Number of Children, Age of Children have a significant relationship with work-life balance. In the second research question, the study explores the level of work-life balance among University women teachers. The level is examined by using descriptive statistics. Overall Respondents had a Moderate level of Work-Life Balance. In the third research question, the study explores the challenges faced by women in maintaining work-life balance under three domains such as Individual factors, Family factors, and Organizational Factors. Overall respondents had moderate levels of challenges due to individual factors, Family Factors, and Organizational factors. Among 8 components

backward regression analysis resulted in 6 significant components affecting work-life balance. Among 8 components backward regression analysis resulted in 5 significant components affecting work-life balance. Among 6 components backward regression analysis resulted in 5 significant components affecting work-life balance. In the fourth research question, the study explores the Impact of Work-Life Balance on Job Satisfaction, Organizational Commitment, Family Satisfaction, and Employee Performance. Overall respondents had a high level of Impact of work-life Balance on Job Satisfaction. Overall respondents had a high level of organizational commitment. Overall respondents had a high level of family satisfaction. Overall respondents had a high level of employee performance. In the Fifth part of the study shows the level of Individual coping practices and strategies adopted by women in maintaining Work-life balance. This was identified using 10 questions. Overall respondents had Moderate levels of Coping. In the sixth part of the study Legislative and judicial provisions enabling Work-life balance were measured using 6 questions. Overall respondents showed moderate levels of legislative and judicial intervention. In the seventh part of the study, the existence of the glass ceiling and its Relationship with work-life balance was measured. Overall respondents expressed a moderate level of existence of Glass Ceiling.

9. RESULTS OF HYPOTHESIS TESTING

H₁1: There is an association between Demographic variables and work-life balance- Hypothesis 1 is accepted.

H₁2: There is a relationship between challenges faced by women and work-life balance.

Sub Hypothesis:

H₁2 (a): There is a relationship between challenges due to Individual factors and Work-life Balance- Sub Hypothesis 2(a) accepted

H₁2 (b): There is a relationship between challenges due to Family factors and Work-life Balance- Sub Hypothesis 2(b) accepted

H₁2 (c): There is a relationship between challenges due to Organizational factors and Work-life Balance – Sub Hypothesis 2(c) accepted

H₁3: Work-life balance has an impact on Job Satisfaction- Hypothesis 3 accepted

H₁4: Work-life balance has an impact on Organizational commitment- Hypothesis 4 accepted

H₁5: Work-life balance has an impact on Family satisfaction -Hypothesis 5 accepted

H₁₆: Work-life balance has an impact on Employee Performance - Hypothesis 6 accepted

H₁₇: There is a relationship between work-life balance and coping strategies adopted by women-Hypothesis 7 accepted

H₁₈: There is a relationship between work-life balance and legislative and judicial interventions- Hypothesis 8 accepted

H₁₉: There is a relationship between the Glass ceiling and Work life balance- Hypothesis 9 accepted

10. CONTRIBUTION OF THE RESEARCH TO SOCIETY

Since the study has revealed the moderate level of work-life balance and glass ceiling among women teachers of State Universities of Karnataka, it is a message to the educated women wanting to build up their career along with giving importance to their individual and family requirements to get into this sector. It has been observed that the number of women teachers in these universities are less compared to Male teachers indicating scope for creating awareness among women as an opportunity in this field.

11. FUTURE SCOPE OF RESEARCH:

Even though the sampling size is acceptable, further studies can be done by increasing the sample size by including Central Universities, private universities and deemed to be universities to see the change in the results of the study. This will improve the universality of the findings. The researchers can take Universities outside Karnataka state as a sampling frame to study the work-life Balance and Glass ceiling. A comparative study related to Work-life balance between Private and Public universities can be studied. The further study can be undertaken on Job stress, Work-Life Balance among working Men and their effects on productivity and job satisfaction.

12. PUBLICATION:

12.1 Publication related to Research Study:

1. Noronha, S., & Aithal, P. S. (2016). Glass Ceiling- A Silent Barrier for Women in Highly Advanced and Humanistic Society. *IRA-International Journal of Management & Social Sciences* (ISSN 2455-2267), 5(3), 455-466. UGC Reference no: 46617
2. Noronha, S., & Aithal, P. S. (2019), "Work Life Balance among Women Employees: A Study on Initiatives Undertaken by Indian Organisations", *MERC Global's International Journal of Management* (ISSN 2321-7278), 7(3), 268-273. UGC Reference no: 49371

3. Noronha, S., & Aithal, P. S. (2017). Organizational Strategic Approach towards Work Life Balance of Women in India. *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS)* (ISSN: 2581-6012), 2(1), 18-24.
4. Noronha, S., & Aithal, P. S. (2019). Work Life Balance and Glass Ceiling of Women Employees – A Literature Review, *Saudi Journal of Business and Management Studies* (ISSN 2415-6663), 2(1), 386-396.
5. Noronha, S., & Aithal, P. S. & M.D. Pradeep. (2017). Study on Policy Framework towards Work Life Balance in India, *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Modern Education (IJMRME)*, (ISSN 2454-6119), 3(2), 11-16
6. Noronha, S., & Aithal, P. S. (2019). Influence of Socio Demographic factors on Work Life Balance (WLB) Among Public Universities Teachers in Karnataka, *International Journal of Scientific Research (IJSR)*, (ISSN 2277-8179), 8(11), 1-4

12.2 Other Publications:

- [1] Aithal P.S. & Noronha. S. (2016). Hitting two birds with one stone: Srinivas university B.Com model in Corporate Auditing, *International Journal of Scientific Research and Modern Education (IJSRME)*, (ISSN: 24555630), 1(1), 853-869.
- [2] M. D. Pradeep & Noronha S. (2016). Study on the Changing landscape of financial Services in Indian Banking System- Opportunities and Challenges, *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Modern Education (IJMTS)*, (ISSN: 25816012), 3(1), 1-10.

12.3 List of Research Papers presented in the Conference:

- [1] Paper on “Glass Ceiling- A Silent Barrier for Women in Highly Advanced and Humanistic Society” in a One day conference on The changing Perspective of Management, IT and social sciences in the contemporary environment at Srinivas Institute of Management studies, Pandeshwar, Mangalore on 07 May 2016.
- [2] Paper on “Challenges for Women in Business and Influence of Market Turbulence” in a one day National Conference on Sustainable Growth in Developing Economies at Srinivas Institute of Management studies, Pandeshwar, Mangalore on 12 April 2012.
- [3] Paper on “Women in Health Sector and Work Life Balance Challenges” in One day National Level conference on Current Development in Computer Science, IT & its impact on Management, Social Sciences and Education at Srinivas Institute of Management studies, Pandeshwar, Mangalore on 26 November 2016.
- [4] Paper on “Study on the Policy Framework towards work life balance in India” in Two day conference - MANEGMA-207, “Reinventing opportunities in Management, IT, & Social Sciences at Srinivas Institute of Management studies, Pandeshwar, Mangalore on 23rd & 24th March 2017.
- [5] Paper on “Glass Ceiling in Top Educational Institutions in India” in a two day workshop on Innovations and Transformations In Banking, Management, IT, Education and Social Sciences at Srinivas Institute of Management studies, Pandeshwar, Mangalore on 26th & 27th August 2016.
- [6] Paper on “Influence of Socio- Demographic factors on Work Life Balance among University Teachers in Karnataka in MANEGMA-2019 A one day national conference on Advances in Management, IT, Education and Social Sciences, Srinivas Institute of Management studies, Pandeshwar, Mangalore on 27th April 2019.

12.4 List of Conferences/ Workshop Attended:

[1] Innovation and transformation in banking, Management, IT, Education and social sciences at Srinivas Institute of Management studies, Pandeshwar on 26th -27th August 2016.

[2] Current Development in computer Science, IT and its impact on Management, social sciences and Education at Srinivas Institute of Management studies, Pandeshwar on 26th November 2016.

[3] Women empowerment 'Shakti 2017' at Ramakrishna Math, Mangaladevi on 12th & 13th January 2017.

[4] One day workshop on Research Methodology and Data Analysis at Srinivas University on 13.07.2019